

FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES OPTIMISED BY THE SYNERGY BETWEEN RUBBER-TOUGHENING AND SiO₂-NANOPARTICLES

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SUMMARY

The performance of fibre-reinforced composites based on epoxy polymers can be improved significantly by combining rubber-toughening with silica nanoparticles. Tough and stiff materials, with improved fatigue and impact behaviour can be manufactured. This is of major interest for aerospace, automotive, shipbuilding or wind turbine blade applications.

Keywords: Epoxy; Nanoparticles; Rubber Toughening; Fracture Performance; Toughening Mechanisms; Fatigue; CFRP.

INTRODUCTION

The epoxy polymers used as adhesives and as the matrices of composite materials are amorphous and highly-crosslinked (thermosetting) materials. This structure results in many useful properties, such as a high modulus and low creep. However, they are relatively brittle materials, with a poor resistance to crack initiation and growth.

Thermosetting materials such as epoxy, vinyl ester or unsaturated polyester are commonly toughened by a micro-phase of a rubbery polymer, e.g. [1-4], without significantly impairing many of the other desirable properties. These rubbers are soluble in the epoxy prior to crosslinking. Hence, as long as the modifiers do not increase the viscosity of the resin significantly, this method of toughening may be used with resin-infusion processes for the production of fibre composite materials. These processes are attractive due to their relatively low tooling costs. However, the addition of these rubbers, at the high concentrations required to achieve significant toughness increases, typically does lead to an unacceptable increase in the viscosity of the epoxy. The loss in modulus related to the rubber toughening (typically around 10% lower) is also undesirable. Therefore, in composites manufacturing, especially when injection methods are involved, this technology is often not used despite the evident benefits for the composite component.

The addition of rigid particles has also been shown to increase the toughness of thermosetting polymers [5-7]. However, these particles have conventionally been tens of microns in diameter, and hence are not suitable for use with resin-infusion processes, as they are larger than the inter-fibre spacing. Indeed, they are strained out of the resin by the fibres during infusion. More recently, the availability of nanometre-sized inorganic particles has allowed rigid particles to be used in the formulation of resins for use with infusion processes, e.g. [8]. Surface-modified silica nanoparticles, available in industrial quantities for a couple of years, are produced as concentrates in epoxy resins such as DGEBA, DGEBF, tetrafunctional epoxy resins or reactive diluents. Vinyl ester resins containing silica nanoparticles are very close to commercialisation. Unlike traditional fillers, the nanoparticles can be used with injection methods, as they do not increase the viscosity. Due to their diameter of 20nm they can penetrate even close-meshed fabrics easily.

By combining rubber toughening with the addition of silica nanoparticles, 'hybrid' resin systems for composites with outstanding properties can be formulated. Tough and stiff materials with superior fatigue properties can be produced. This technology is suitable for vinyl ester resin systems as well as for epoxies. The modified resins can be used in prepregging, wet lay-up, filament winding or injection techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy resin used was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), 'DER332' (Dow) or 'LY556' (Huntsman). The organosilane-modified silica nanoparticles were obtained at 40wt% in DGEBA, 'Nanopox F400' (Nanoresins), and had an average particle size of about 20nm [9]. The curing agent was an accelerated methylhexahydrophthalic acid anhydride, 'Albidur HE 600' (Nanoresins), and a stoichiometric amount was used. The reactive liquid carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN) rubber was obtained as an adduct with a concentration of 40wt% in DGEBA, 'Albipox 1000' (Nanoresins). Bulk sheets of polymer were produced, and cured for 1 hour at 90°C, plus 2 hours at 160°C.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was performed using a MultiMode scanning probe microscope from Veeco. A smooth surface was prepared by cutting with an ultramicrotome. The glass transition temperature, T_g , was measured using differential scanning calorimetry at a rate of 10°C/min. Tensile dumbbell specimens were tested according to the ISO standard test method [10]. The single-edge notch bend (SENB) test was used to determine the fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of the polymers [11]. A Carl Zeiss Leo 1525 field emission gun scanning electron microscope was used to observe the fracture surfaces. Fatigue tests were conducted using compact tension specimens, with a displacement ratio, $\delta_{min}/\delta_{max}$, of 0.5. Sinusoidal loading was used, with a frequency of 5Hz. The rate of cyclic-fatigue growth per cycle, da/dN , was measured [12] as a function of the range of applied stress-intensity factor, ΔK_I .

The CFRP composite panels were manufactured by vacuum-assisted resin-transfer moulding (VARTM) using selected formulations. The carbon fibre was an isotropic linen-weave fibre fabric arranged in a 0/90° pattern with a density of 168g/m², supplied by Lange-Ritter. The average volume fraction of the fibres in the carbon-fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates was 26.5%. A thin film of

poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) was inserted into the fabric prior to resin infusion, along one side of the CFRP plate to a length of 35mm, to act as a starter crack for the fracture specimens.

Flexural modulus tests on the composites were conducted in three point bending [13], at a strain rate of 0.01min^{-1} . Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens were used to measure the mode I fracture energy, G_{IC} [14] of the composites at a test rate of 1mm/min.

MICROSTRUCTURE

Atomic force microscopy and transmission electron microscopy of the bulk samples showed that the materials were homogeneous, and that the nanoparticles were well dispersed throughout the epoxy matrix, see Figure 1 for example. There was no agglomeration of the silica nanoparticles, even at higher volume fractions of silica nano.

Figure 1. AFM height image of the epoxy polymer containing silica nanoparticles.

Figure 2. AFM phase image of the epoxy polymer containing 9wt% CTBN and 10wt% silica nanoparticles.

The CTBN undergoes reaction-induced phase-separation upon curing of the epoxy to form rubbery particles of about $0.5\mu\text{m}$ in diameter, as is well documented for such materials [1-4]. The addition of the silica nanoparticles, to form the hybrid, did not change this morphology, see Figure 2.

RESULTS - BULK

Mechanical Properties

The glass transition temperature of about 140°C was unchanged by the addition of the nanoparticles, see Table 1. The addition of 9wt% CTBN can reduce T_g , which indicates that some rubber remains dissolved in the epoxy rather than phase-separating to form particles. There are no significant changes in the T_g of the epoxy containing CTBN and

the various concentrations of the nanoparticles, which suggests that the volume fraction of the rubber particles is independent of the concentration of silica.

A tensile modulus of approximately 3GPa was measured for the unmodified epoxy, see Table 1. The measured tensile modulus, E , was found to increase steadily with the nanoparticle content, as the modulus of silica, $E=70\text{GPa}$ [15], is much greater than that of the epoxy polymer. As expected the modulus of the epoxy decreases with the addition of the soft CTBN rubber. The addition of silica nanoparticles to the rubber-modified epoxy allows much of this reduction in modulus to be recovered, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermal, mechanical and fracture properties of the epoxy-polymer matrices.

Formulation		T_g (°C)	E (GPa)	K_{IC} (MPam ^{1/2})
wt% nanoparticles	wt% CTBN			
0.0	0.0	143	2.96	0.59
4.1	0.0	137	3.20	1.03
7.8	0.0	136	3.42	1.17
11.1	0.0	141	3.57	1.18
14.8	0.0	138	3.60	1.29
20.2	0.0	138	3.85	1.42
0.0	9.0	126	2.44	1.11
2.3	9.0	133	2.66	1.71
4.5	9.0	135	2.77	1.70
9.0	9.0	129	2.79	1.76
10.5	9.0	126	2.80	1.99

Fracture Properties

A fracture toughness of about $0.6\text{MPam}^{1/2}$ was measured for the unmodified epoxy, which is typical for an unmodified thermoset in the glassy region. The addition of silica nanoparticles increased significantly the fracture toughness, see Table 1. The addition of rubber also increased the toughness, but the hybrid-toughened epoxies gave the highest bulk K_{IC} values and showed a considerable synergistic toughening effect. A maximum K_{IC} of almost $2\text{MPam}^{1/2}$ was measured.

Toughening Mechanisms

The rubbery particles greatly increase the toughness of the epoxy via interactions of the stress field ahead of the crack tip and the rubbery particles which leads to greatly enhanced plastic deformation of the epoxy matrix [2-4, 16].

Scanning electron microscopy of the fracture surfaces of the silica-modified epoxy showed that the epoxy debonds from the nanoparticles, with subsequent void growth, see Figure 3. There was no evidence of crack pinning or crack deflection; indeed these mechanisms will not occur with 20nm diameter particles as the particles are smaller than the crack opening displacement [17].

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrograph of the fracture surface of epoxy polymer containing silica nanoparticles. (Some voids with nanoparticles are circled).

Fatigue Performance

Figure 4 shows typical cyclic-fatigue results for the unmodified epoxy polymer and for the material containing 7.8wt% of nanoparticles [18]. There is a region where there is a linear relationship between the logarithmic crack growth rate per cycle, da/dN , versus the logarithmic range of applied stress-intensity factor, ΔK_I , i.e. the ‘Paris Law region’. There is also a clear threshold region, denoted ΔK_{th} , below which no cyclic-fatigue crack growth will occur. This threshold value is a useful parameter for material development and the design engineer. The fatigue performance of the epoxy is clearly enhanced by the silica nanoparticles, and the value of ΔK_{th} is increased significantly due to the addition of 7.8wt% of silica nanoparticles.

Figure 4. Logarithmic crack growth rate per cycle, da/dN , versus logarithmic range of applied stress-intensity factor, ΔK_I , from the cyclic-fatigue tests.

RESULTS - COMPOSITE

Mechanical Properties

There is little difference between the flexural modulus of the composites manufactured using the different formulations. As would be expected, the modulus of the CFRP laminates is dominated by the presence of the carbon-fibre weave, giving a value of E of approximately 26GPa in all cases.

The glass transition temperature, T_g , of the control composite was 135°C. The addition of rubber or silica nanoparticles has little effect on the T_g of the epoxy, which was 133 ±4°C for all the composites. These values agree well with the bulk T_g values.

Fracture Properties

The fracture tests gave a mean value of G_{IC} (interlaminar) equal to about 440J/m² for the composite using the unmodified epoxy matrix. The presence of the silica nanoparticles alone (at a concentration of 11.9wt%) had no significant effect on the delamination resistance. The addition 9wt% of CTBN rubber alone did lead to an increase in the measured fracture energy to 1050J/m². However, the further addition of nanoparticles to the rubber-toughened epoxy, giving a range of hybrid-toughened epoxy matrices, gave a further enhancement of the toughness, with a highest value of G_{IC} (interlaminar) of 1320J/m² being recorded.

The fracture energy, G_{IC} , of the bulk materials was calculated from the values of K_{IC} and E to allow comparison with the measured composite fracture energies. The relationship between the values of G_{IC} (interlaminar) of the CFRP laminates and G_{IC} of the bulk matrices is shown in Figure 5. (Note that the wt% of the nanoparticles stated is the average value for some of the formulations given in Table 1, since an exact correspondence between the composite and bulk matrix tests was not always obtained.) The results shown in Figure 5 clearly reveal the significant toughening of both the composite and bulk materials by the rubbery phase present in the epoxy polymer. The further enhanced values of G_{IC} (interlaminar) and G_{IC} of the bulk matrices when the hybrid-toughened epoxy polymers are employed is also shown. Thus, the synergistic effect of having a multiphase structure based upon both silica nanoparticles and micron-sized rubbery domains is clearly demonstrated.

Figure 5. Fracture energy, G_{IC} (interlaminar), for the CFRP laminates versus G_{IC} (bulk) for the matrices. Values of the glass transition temperature are also shown.

Fatigue and Impact Performance

The improvements in the fatigue performance of the bulk matrices are also seen for the composite laminates. Tension-tension fatigue tests gave an increased number of cycles to failure when silica nanoparticles were added. The hybrid materials showed the best fatigue performance, e.g. [19,20]

The CFRP laminates were also investigated using a falling-dart impact test, with a 30J impact. The delamination area after impact was determined from ultrasonic scans according to the AITM standard (Airbus Test Method) 1-0010, "Determination of Compression Strength after Impact". The best overall performance was shown by the hybrid system with both rubber and nanoparticle modification, where the falling dart impact performance improved by 36%. This laminate also showed a superior surface finish, probably due to reduced shrinkage. Figure 6 shows the C-scans and photographs of the laminate after impact for the control and the epoxy containing both CTBN rubber and silica nanoparticles.

Figure 6. C-Scan of delamination area and photograph of surface of CFRP laminates after 30J impact for control and hybrid CTBN/silica nanoparticle system.

CONCLUSIONS

Silica nanoparticles have been shown to toughen an epoxy polymer. The modulus is increased, but T_g is unaffected. The toughening mechanisms were considered, and crack deflection and crack pinning were discounted. The microscopy showed evidence of debonding of the nanoparticles and subsequent plastic void growth. For toughening to occur, the matrix must be able to deform sufficiently to allow shear bands to form. The fracture toughness and fatigue performance are both improved. The addition of CTBN rubber increases the measured fracture toughness, but reduces the modulus and T_g of the bulk material.

The use of silica nanoparticles and micron-sized rubbery particles to form hybrid-toughened epoxy polymers has been shown to give a range of novel materials. These can be used to manufacture composite laminates by resin transfer moulding. The presence of the rubber and nanoparticles does not significantly decrease the flexural modulus or the glass transition temperature of the composite. However, these formulations show a significant increase in the bulk toughness. The interlaminar fracture energy of carbon-fibre reinforced composites is also increased. The fatigue and impact performance are also improved. The synergistic effect of having a multiphase structure based upon both silica nanoparticles and micron-sized rubbery domains has been demonstrated. Hence this hybrid system shows the best balance of properties.

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